

Rabbit Fur Processing And Dyeing Process

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Abstract: *In this article, research was carried out on the cultivation of rabbit fur and the process of processing it, practical implementation skills were formed. Also, the article contains information that practical experiments were carried out on two different types of rabbit fur, namely canned and non-canned (freshly slaughtered rabbit skin) sample.*

Keywords — rabbit, fur, pekil, mezdra, razbivka, otkatka, chilling, hrom, rabbit farming, apilka, dublina, dye, drum, acid, cooking, canned..

INTRODUCTION.

Modern designers who produce rabbit products do not lag behind fashion trends and, developing day by day, provide consumers with an increasingly wide and original assortment of rabbit fur products. They are distinguished by their models, colors and quality and choice. Rabbit fur is considered universal. In terms of the degree of heat preservation, it stands in line with many valuable furs. Such clothes are sewn from natural or artificial fur. Natural fur shubas (sheepskin - for example muton, Astrakhan, sigeyka v.x.) are sewn from the skin of Northern Fox, samurai, shinshiilla, bear, wolf, sucker, nutria, rabbit, diamond, Sea Cat, Beaver, reindeer, ohu, Beaver, Jaguar, pony horse, Canadian buck, snow leopard, etc.[1]

Rabbit fur tanning is a step-by-step process of processing the skin in chemical solutions. The oiled fur turns into a semihomashyo and the possibility of making products from it arises. We conducted an experiment on the process of fur augmentation.[2]

In this regard, it is recommended to carry out short-term pre-soaking at a temperature of 20-25 C° for 3-5 hours. Effective humidifiers - surfactants and antiseptics-are added to the washing liquid to facilitate the removal of contaminants. At this stage of processing, it is very important to correctly select the surfactant.[3]

Currently, the fur industry processes more than 20 different types of fur raw materials in significant quantities. Each type of fur raw material has its own structural features and requires an individual approach to processing. For this reason, it is not recommended to combine the processing of different types of fur in one production batch. In addition to being by type, fur is separated into different production batches according to the way of storing raw materials, the size of their skins, the thickness of leather fabrics, wool, etc.[4]

The next important processes for tanning rabbit skin are hair washing and degreasing. The need for these processes is associated with a high content of fatty substances in the skin. The oil located on the surface of the hair has strong

hydrophobic properties due to its chemical nature. It is designed to protect hair from the influence of any external factors.[5]

Intermediate washing for most types of raw materials is carried out between the first and second soaking. This will help the second hydration go well and at the same time facilitate subsequent washing and degreasing processes. Due to the different nature of hair oil and skin tissue, preparations to remove them from the skin are also very different. For degreasing, an emulsion method is used using a certain type of surfactant. Surfactants should have a number of qualities: the ability to moisturize and wash, the emulsion and distribution of fatty substances.[6]

In addition to surfactants, non-ionic drugs are used in degreasing for the stability of the emulsions formed during the washing process. They effectively wash away oils from skin tissue, and also allow the resulting emulsion to stabilize and prevent fatty substances from the skin from getting on the surface of hair or skin tissue during drainage and subsequent washing. Due to the combined use of a combination of anionactive and non-ionic surfactants, it is enough that the degreasing process is carried out in a compound of 1-2 g/l components.[7]

Currently, picelling using organic acids is the most common. This is because, despite the high affinity of mineral acids (such as chloride and sulfur) for collagen, the main protein of the skin, such acids are not evenly distributed throughout the protein structure. For this reason, the skins are not evenly spaced. The advantage of organic acids is that they are more effective in extracting proteins. Organic acids, unlike mineral acids, do not create such a low level of value, therefore, in the process of subsequent acidification, an increase in basicity can be carried out more gently, which helps to maintain the softness of the semi-finished product.[8]

With any pikel method, after the end of the process, softening of the skin is achieved in about a day. Tanningprocessing of skin and fur with special substances, solutions, shedding (peeling) of skin wool.[9]

The keying stage in fur trimming is to give them color. Dyeing is a set of physicochemical and mechanical processes

that ensure that the dye substance is applied to the surface or that it is included in the skin and fur. When painting, the requirements for saturation, uniformity, time and coloring in relation to external influences must be met. The painting technology is determined according to the type of equipment and the paint class as follows.[10]

1. Dye Hair with acid dyes.
2. Application and assortment of acid paints.

Acid dyes are dyes whose general characteristic is the sodium salts of aromatic sulfuric acids. Acid dyes include dye classes such as mono-azo dyes, Poly-azo dyes, anthraquinone dyes, and some representatives of other classes. Thanks to this variety, acidic dyes allow you to dye hair in a wide color scheme. Unlike oxidizing dyes, acid dyes have very little toxicity.[10]

All acid dyes have an affinity for protein fibers. Due to their structure, they bind to protein molecules with several types of bonds (Ionic, hydrogen, Van der Waals forces). Thanks to this, both hair and skin texture can be colored with acidic dyes, and as a result, the color is distinguished by Shine and purity. Acid paints consist of molecules of a complex structure, therefore, a number of conditions are required for painting: high temperature, special leveling reagents, preparation of the semifinished product for the painting process. The penetration of dye into the hair structure is greatly influenced by the size of the dye molecule.[11]

3. Preparation of semi-finished product for painting: the optimal temperature for painting with acid is 65-70°C. However, it should be remembered that in order to preserve the plastic properties of the skin tissue, all processes must be carried out at a temperature 25-30 ° C lower than the welding temperature of the skin tissue.

4. The influence of various factors on the dyeing process: as mentioned above, several main factors influence the dyeing process. One of the most important is the painting temperature. Dyeing at a temperature of 65-70 °C is carried out in the optimal mode, since keratin swelling and decay of the dye occur, which contributes to the spread of the dye to the hair structure. When the temperature drops, the dye molecules accumulate, which makes it difficult for them to spread to the hair structure and leads to a decrease in color intensity and the ingress of dye into the skin tissue.

When dealing with rabbits, you can not only grow the required number of rabbits, but also process their fur yourself. This will bring a good additional income. The increase in the desired quality level of the resulting fur is achieved only if all the necessary requirements are met.[12]

At the beginning of the process, we took 51 pieces of rabbit fur to increase in an hour with Slaughter. Their total weight was measured, 51 pieces came out 16.5 kg. After bringing the skin, fat and muscle residues were immediately removed. This was done with a blunt knife, pulling the skin into a special device. The method of holding the knife perpendicular to the skin was followed. Accordingly, within an hour, the process of overclocking began. There will be no exaggeration if I say that

we were able to achieve a very effective result in the process. Received the fact that the quality level does not deteriorate, a variety of bacterial falls, no unpleasant odors appear, the state of moisture cannot burn, hair loss, premature rotting of the skin. As a result of the practice carried out through modern methods of enhancing rabbit fur when hulking, the shelf life of rabbit fur was achieved at the required level, obtaining a product of light, soft and flexible, odorless, high-quality and bright colors.[13]

As a conclusion, we can say that in Uzbekistan now the rapid development of rabbit breeding with pictures is taking place, obtaining rabbit fur of all varieties. Based on the results of the experiment, it can be argued that if the process of qualitative tanning of rabbit fur is established, it will be possible to get to the world market by producing modern products from them. can affect conditions caused by a particular situation.[18]

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